

Immersive Soundscapes- Redefining E-commerce with Interactive Music

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ABSTRACT

The use of music within a physical retail setting is commonplace, and its effects upon consumer behavior have been well documented [1]. However, similar use of music within an ecommerce context has been largely avoided. At Bose, we experimented with the use of *interactive* music on a retail landing page, with the goal of understanding whether it would influence overall conversions.

A small user study was performed to measure the effect on ecommerce metrics and brand perception, and the results showed positive scores in both domains. This opened a wider discussion about the potential applications of music within ecommerce, the problem of controlling user context, and possible future applications of music within digital retail.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2023, Bose launched its new flagship earbuds with an interactive landing page. Drawing upon inspiration from Apple, the page contained animations controlled by the user's scrolling, along with a modern design and dynamic imagery aimed at engaging customers emotionally. In service of providing more immersion, an interactive music layer was added to the page. Several looping tracks were created to evoke the tone of the brand, each one composed to match the visuals at specific points on the page. The loops were tempo-synced and set to crossfade as the user scrolled up and down the page. Low pass filter sweeps were added to the intro and outro of the page, in concert with visual "curtain" effects, giving the user an additional layer of audio control as they scrolled. A mute button allowed users to toggle the experience (initial state upon page load was muted).

Although the experience was well received by the creative team, the audio layer was deemed too risky for a flagship product launch. Instead, the experience was sent for user testing.

2. TESTING

Ten users were shown the page via UserZoom: 50% male, 50% female. All were US-based and were premium earbud owners. Each participant was asked to scroll through the page without audio, then asked to scroll through it again with audio. After each experience, they were presented with a questionnaire.

The key findings were:

1. Consumer engagement scores increased when the page was viewed with the audio experience (i.e. users spent more overall time on the page and interacted more with individual elements).
2. Scroll depth increased when the page was viewed with the audio experience (one user commented "I don't like scrolling because it quickly makes me bored, but the audio kept me scrolling").
3. When asking users if the audio improved their browsing experience on a scale of 1-7, the majority of users rated it a 6 or 7. However, when discussing their reasoning, none of them thought the audio was a driving factor in making a purchase on the site.
4. The majority of users preferred the experience with sound turned on but noted that they were unlikely to listen to the audio unless initially incentivized.
5. The majority of users thought the experience made sense within the context of an audio brand like Bose, and one user commented that no other retailers were offering such experiences.
6. Keywords describing the page *without* audio were: innovative, edgy, new, modern, futuristic, high tech, quality
7. Keywords describing the page *with* audio were: unique, dynamic, clever, fun, engaging, original, appealing

3. CONCLUSIONS

The audio experience on the page was well-received, with most users describing it using positive keywords and favorable ratings. Additionally, metrics for consumer engagement and scroll depth were higher with the audio experience turned on- both of which are indicators for higher conversion rates.

However, there was no direct impact on conversion sentiment, and while many users regarded the experience as fun and interesting, none of them considered it necessary for their purchase journey. As a result, the experimental nature of the audio layer, and the potential impact on Core Web Vitals (i.e. page load time) led the business to release the page without music.

4. DISCUSSION

While the interactive audio experience wasn't released to market, the modest success of this experiment opened the door to further questioning:

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Web Audio Conference WAC-2024, March 15-17, 2024, West Lafayette, IN, USA.

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Why is the use of music ubiquitous in the brick-and-mortar retail world, but absent in ecommerce?

The problem is that in physical retail, *user context* is controlled, whereas online, it is not [2]. Brick and mortar stores act as carefully curated spaces, wherein customers experience a combination of sights, smells, and sounds all carefully crafted to work together. In the world of songwriting, this emotional coherence is known as *prosody* [3], and it allows the music to take hold and positively influence consumer behavior.

In a digital setting, the user's physical space, audio device, human company and mood are all unknown. Someone browsing the web on their smartphone while commuting by rail has a different user context than someone shopping at home with the TV in the background and family members in the room. Musical prosody is much harder to achieve, and as a result, audio experiences can feel intrusive.

Despite the problem of user context, there still seems to be an untapped opportunity to bridge the musical gap between physical and digital retail.

If implemented in the correct manner, could the power of music be leveraged within an ecommerce setting to motivate consumer spending?

There are several avenues to explore:

- Gaming. The experience of gaming is similar to browsing the web. Given the popularity of mobile games, it should also be susceptible to the problem of user context. However, game audio is turned on by default, because the user's *expectation* is to be immersed. Could ecommerce customers be prompted to change their expectations of the shopping experience, in order to bring audio to the forefront? Perhaps offering a coupon or discount in exchange for their consent for immersion?
- TikTok. Platforms like TikTok are changing the linear experience of ecommerce and bridging the gap between

entertainment and shopping. According to TikTok's Head of Industry, Simon Hofmeiser, "It's a 'sound on' platform by default and dominates the user's attention. You do not 'check' TikTok, you watch TikTok. It's not a second screen" [4]. What role is music playing in this space, and can it be replicated on the web?

- Apple Vision Pro. While the current browsing experience inside of Apple's AR headset is still 2D, it's not hard to imagine a future state where the web starts to become a 3D experience, complete with spatial audio. Will the future of ecommerce be an AR store projected into your living room, complete with some of the curated elements borrowed from physical retail—like music?
- Think smaller. Perhaps audio in ecommerce isn't a major characteristic of the page, but something more subtle. Could small bits of sound design be used as a lubricant to help the user through key moments of confusion on the shopping journey? E-retailers are constantly tweaking and optimizing the user journey to squeeze more revenue out of every click. If audio can be shown to ease the path to the cart for even 1% of customers, it could translate into sizable profits.

5. REFERENCES

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